

Unorganized Sector and Social Security of Migrant Workers in India

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Abstract

Migrant workers are the most vulnerable lot. They face double whammy for being migrant and labour. They are exploited by their employer. The laws are in place, but there are flaws in them. Even the good laws are implemented half hearted. There is a need to give more teeth to the laws and also implement the relevant laws with full force.

Keywords: Migration, Social Security, Unorganized Sector, Workers

Migration of workers is a common human phenomenon especially from backward states in India. In search of livelihood source and happy life have been prime drivers of migration. Migration of workers has profound and deep implications on their lives, their family, receiving states, sending states and nation as a whole. Migrations have economic genesis but it causes socio-political cultural ramifications. It has been found that mingling of different cultures has had positive ramification, besides putting an strain on the culture and life of the upcoming society affected in either way by migration.

Migration is a very complex and multidimensional issue. Therefore, this paper shall confine to the issues of the non-skilled and semi-skilled migrant workers specially construction and domestic migrant workers.

Migration is a widely perceived feature of human and the migrants try to survive in the most testing conditions both natural and man-made. Migration in India has existed since time immemorial. Migration has assumed special significance for the country and the society especially in the context of globalization and opening up of the world economy. Widening gulf between rich and poor, inequality, income disparities, agrarian distress, inadequate employment generation, vast growth of informal economy and the resultant migration from rural areas to urban, urban to urban and backward to comparatively advanced regions in the most appalling conditions have been witnessed since India embraced liberalisation, globalisation and privatisation.

Unorganized sector employ approximately 80 million

Migrant Workers in India, who are deprived of even the bare minimum of basic human rights¹. Irregular employment, lack of opportunities or very limited opportunities are some of the common in rural India. It has led to the seasonal migration for worker. It has been estimated that approximately 120 million people or more migrate from rural areas to urban labour markets, industries and farms². It has become essential for the people from regions that face frequent shortages of rainfall or suffer floods, or where population densities are high in relation to land, limited or no opportunities are available. Areas such as Kashmir, North East, facing unresolved social or political conflicts also lead to high out migration. Poverty, lack of local options are some of the push factors of migration whereas the availability of work elsewhere become the pull factor of migration. Migration is deemed to have happened, when a person engage himself or herself in a remunerative activity in a place of which he is not a native or national.

CURRENT STATUS OF MIGRATION

Social structures and patterns of development, disadvantaged geographical locations etc are the prime drivers of out migration in India. The development policies the government post-Independence have accelerated the process of out migration. Uneven development of the regions, states is the main cause of migration. Besides this there are the disparities among classes, castes, inter regions and amongst different socio-economic classes. The landless poor who mostly belong to lower castes, indigenous communities and economically backward regions are compelled by their livelihood question to migrate. It has been observed that the process of globalisation and the intrusion in the tribal areas in the name of the development, opening up of new industries has led to the displacements of the local tribal people.

Moreover, deforestation also played a major role in migration. One of the research study has revealed that about 77% of the population i.e. nearly 840 million Indians live on less than Rs.20 a day³. Indian agriculture, which was once the mainstay of the masses mainly the rural populace has become non remunerative, non-rewarding today due to the apathy and policy failure of the government. One of the research study has estimated that the lives of 100,000 peasants were lost during the period from 1996 to 2003, which translates into suicide of an Indian peasant every 45 minutes. However, majority of the farmer's suicides were reported from the developed states like Gujarat, Maharashtra etc. It can be a separate topic of research. Large scale migration not only from the rural areas but also from urban areas of the states Bihar, Orissa, Uttar Pradesh migrate in search of the livelihood mainly in the informal sector, low end jobs, seasonal work. About 70% of the ground level workforce in the factories of Ahmedabad are migrant workers, they largely remains invisible because there are no official records of the migrants maintained either by source or destination states⁴.

Some regions like UP and Bihar have been known for rural migration for decades, the bandwagon has been joined by the states like Odisha, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and recently even North East became major sending regions of manual labour. Among the biggest employers of migrant workers is the construction sector (40 million), domestic work (20 million), textile (11 million), brick kiln work (10 million), transportation, mines & quarries and agriculture, sex workers (2 millions), 5 call girls (5 millions) illegal mines (12 million) otherwise called small scale mines. International migration of unskilled and semi-skilled workers have also accentuated. Middle East countries employ large chunk of the migrants. At present around 5.5 million Indians are working in the oil exporting countries of the Middle-East and another 2 million are working in the developed countries.

Managed in many cases by private labour contractors and fuelled by social networks there are well formed patterns in movement of labour across hundreds of kilometres within the country. Figure 1: Major net migration flows, 2001 (IIPS 2001)⁵.

Migration through the lens of census

It is estimated that 60% of migrants changing their residences within their district of birth and 20% within their own states, while the rest move across the other states boundaries.

Table 1: Estimated migrant workers according to census

Census Year	No. of migrant workers (in million)
1971	167
1981	213
1991	232
2001	315
Source: Census Year (1971 to 2001)ⁱ	

A study was commissioned by Social alert and discovered that alarming 92% of the domestic workers are women, girls and children and 20% of these females are under 14 years of age. There is a perceptible phenomenon in this migration, that is, the tremendous increase of women workers migrating either individually or in groups to find work. They are travelling very long distances even for short-term employment, in the absence of any prospect or promise of employment, still they are migrating. This is a disturbing trend, as in the event of not getting employment, they end up as victims of sexual abuse. Even if they get employment, they have to work under inhuman conditions.

CONSTRUCTION SECTOR AND MIGRANT WORKERS

Since when India adopted LPP policy it has unleashed

has unleashed wide spread construction activities. Currently construction sector is the largest employer of the migrant workers with the approximately 40 million workers are engaged in it. The working hours are from dusk to the dawn. The work hour often stretches from 14 to 16 hours for male and for female workers it even more gruelling with the additional responsibility of the looking after the household chores. It was discovered that there are normal flouting of the rules of migrants workers in the constructions sites. There is lack of security, compensation for injuries, access to drinking water and health care for the workers on the worksite.

Though the Building and Construction Workers Act 1996 was enacted, but half-hearted implementation has led to the increasing woes of the construction workers. It has been discovered that there is no awareness of this Act among the workers and even their employers and their supervisors at worksites. This Act has a workers welfare cess pool, but most of the collected money has been remain dormant in the pool as the benefits are not reaching to the workers. It has been also discovered that there is almost not awareness among construction workers about this Act and about the provision of the workers welfare fund collected through the cess. In many of the cases, it has been found that EPF of the works are deducted and the workers are unaware that they need to claim it after a certain period or on maturity.

GLOBALISATION AND MIGRANTS WORKERS

There is no respite in outmigration. In fact the pace of migration has quickened after the implementation of the liberalisation, privatisation and globalisation (LPG) policy in July 1991. This is a clear pointers to the fact that LPG policy has led to the development of the selected regions, where the companies preferred to invest their money. In fact the policy of the govern-

ment has also accentuated the outmigration. Conditions of the migrant workers have become precarious and vulnerable on the face of the diluting of the labour laws and social security schemes for the workers.

In the name of the ease of doing business, they have been left at the mercy of the employer. They are subjected to long hours of work without adequate social security. The employer has also upper hand and flout even the basic labour and social security norms without impunity. Local workers have even some clout and say. But the migrant workers are most vulnerable lot in the places they work. They are working like slaves and reduced to a machine. The biggest of the sufferers of the LPG policy seems are the migrant workers.

But it cannot be denied that LPG has also brought them some benefits in terms of the employment, learning new work and life skills, monetary rewards to

support their own and their families' livelihood. But there is much desired on the part of the government to work on the schemes focused on welfare of the informal migrant workers.

There conditions grow from bad to worse where there accident on the construction sites. In absence of flouting of the rules, India has recorded the world's highest accident rate among construction workers. According to International Labour Organization 165 out of every 1,000 workers are injured on the job.

There are number of intermediaries in the construction sector. It can be imagined when there are multiple intermediaries, how the sucking and parasitic the system becomes. The small and petty contractors who are outsourced by the mid-sized contractors, who in turn are outsourced by principal employer leave no opportunity to exploit labours.

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CONSTRUCTION SECTOR AND GENDER DISPARITY

Women are not behind to male migrants. Women are almost half of the interstate migrant workforce. Women constitute more than 1/3rd in the construction industry. The division of labour is gendered in the construction industry. Women are mainly engaged in non-skilled work in this sector. Male workers dominate

skilled jobs like masonry, carpentry and other skilled jobs. Women work like collie, porter carry head-loads of brick, sand, stone, cement and water to the masons. They also carry work materials to skilled workers like carpenters etc. There are wage differentials of male and female, and it is sometime practices even in cases of nature of job being same for both the sex. Women are paid much lower wages compared to their male counterpart.

Figure 1: Disparity in daily wages of informal sector workers aged 15-59 years (in Rs.)

Source: National Sample Survey Organisation¹, 68th Round, 2011-12.

This disparity is not only practiced in construction industry, but this is a common practice in other industry also. Like in the mining sector women do unskilled jobs above ground. They do not get any paid leave and they run the risk of losing wages and also may lose employment for taking long duration leave. They are highly prone to sexual harassments often by

their employer and sometime also by their male co-workers. Some studies have reported that only 15% of the cases of sexual assault are reported. However, actual number may be much high. They are not formally not reported so they are not on record. So there is a chance that they are under reported. There is no awareness on the Vishakha guideline issued by the

Supreme Court. Rules are openly flouted and women are not provided with any extra facilities to take care of their children while they are working. Despite so much of the exploitation and due to the absence of the opportunities in their own native places they have no option but to migrate.

MIGRANT DOMESTIC WORKERS

There are 20 million domestic workers mostly migrants from rural India. It has been reported that 92% of the 20 million domestic workers are women and children and 20% of these females are under 14 years of age. Regular streams of new migrants leave behind families in Bihar, Orissa, Chattisgarh, Jharkhand, Assam, and Mizoram for Mumbai, Delhi and other cities. They are desperate to join the army of domestic workers in other places in the absence of fruitful work in their native villages or town. They are readily eager to grab any job work for much less than those who are already working. They are silent sufferers and victims of constant verbal and sexual abuse and they do not possess any grievance redressal mechanism at their disposal.

They often work for the rich people in cities. The case of the Bengal workers and employer at Mahagun society in Noida was widely reported in the news. The police has held some of the workers on the charge of leading the attack on the society¹. Their poor class status and precarious conditions being outside of the native place, and moreover their dependence on their masters for their livelihood had left them in a utterly vulnerable position. The police has also arrested some of the workers at the instance of their employer. The police also acted on partisan manner. Media has also played partisan role by labelling them as Bangladeshis. Whereas, they are natives of West Bengal and hold Indian citizen.

MIGRATION AND RURAL EMPLOYMENT SCHEMES

Numerous schemes have been implemented to address the rural poverty and stem the migration from the rural areas. But no policy seems to work on the ground to address the issue of rural poverty, inequality, distress migration. Government of India pledge to reduce the poverty by half by 2015 under Millennium Development Goal. On this commitment, the government of India has implemented very ambitious scheme Mahatma Gandhi Rural Employment Guarantee scheme (MGNREGS) in 2005.

Of late the government has tried to stem the migration and generate local employment through implementation of the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MGNREGS). To very limited extent it has been able to stem the tide of the outmigration. Mainly the old, infirm, female are the participants in this scheme, whereas the young prefer not to work under this scheme due to the poor remuneration, irregular work availability, delay in wage payments etc. Wide bungling, corruption and siphoning off the funds have been reported from this scheme, which as a result has marred to the potentialities of this scheme.

Withering social security for the migrant workers

Their situation is made worse by local governments' brutal eviction drives dislocating and destabilizing the lives of the very people without whom the cities would come to a crippling halt². They have to live in makeshift tents with plastic covers. They have no option but to bathe and defecate out in the open. They are at double disadvantage as they do not possess Public Distribution System (PDS) Cards and hence are forced to buy food grains and kerosene at higher than market prices. Since they are also absent from their native place, they also cannot also available the benefits of

the available social security and other government schemes like PDS etc. The ruling elite are very insensitive and unable to recognise that child labour is a natural consequence of migrations.

Flaws in Legal Provisions and half-hearted implementation

The Government of India enacted Inter-state Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act 1979. The act covers only interstate migrants. It stipulates that contractors must pay timely wages equal or higher than the minimum wage, provide suitable residential accommodation, prescribed medical facilities, protective clothing, notify accidents and casualties to specified authorities and kin. The principal employer shall be responsible for providing all the facilities and entitlements as stipulated in the act. The Act provides for adjudication of industrial disputes in the provincial jurisdiction where they work or in their home province. The act also stipulates penalties including, fine or imprisonment or both for non-compliance.

However, the act provides an escape route to principal employers if they are able to prove that transgressions were committed without their knowledge. There is no need to reiterate that the Act is another proverbial paper tiger and not much can be shown on the ground. Very few cases of flouting of the law is reported. That too are not translated into prosecutions.

CONCLUSION

The migrant labourers face double whammy as they are both labourers and migrants. Hence, there is no improvement in the working and living conditions for migrant workers. There are no structures to adequately address the basic issues concerning migrant labour relations, leave aside, addressing the whole gamut of labour relations. Laws are in place, but they are flawed.

Even the good provisions can't be implemented. It seems they are implemented only to flout them. The Indian Judiciary sometimes came to the rescue of migrant labour and makes pronouncements and observations to fill the gap in the justice delivery system.

The Employees State Insurance Act, 1948 and the Employees Provident Fund Miscellaneous Provision Act, 1952 can be considered as landmark legislations, besides Building and Construction workers Act, Inter-state Migration Workers Act etc. Such enactments have targeted the fundamental problems of labour including migrant labour by such provisions which take care of the workers in the exigencies of sickness, ill-health and other contingencies of life including old age. There is a need to strengthen these laws and implement them in letter and spirit. Further MNREGA is very promising, which guarantees 100 days of employment in a year. More fund should be allocated, the effort should be made to provide regular and seamless work to the workers at the local places. This will reduce the phenomenon of the migration.

To alleviate the condition of the construction workers and improving their lot need concerted effort from all the stakeholders and cooperation and coordination between the government and other social actors including the trade unions. There is a need to openly involve the interested NGO's working for the migrant labours. There should be adequate provisions of fund to these NGOs. Some funds from the construction workers cess may be earmarked for the NGOs to improve the lot of the construction workers. Similarly, cess may also be imposed on employers of other workers on the line of the Building and Construction workers act. Besides this there is a need to restore some rights of the labour unions for which strong will is needed on the part of the government.

REFERENCES

- 1 Kumar, Bhavya (2015), Migrant Workers: An In-visible Community of 80 Million; <https://www.innovairre.com/migrant-workers-invisible-community-80-million/> (accessed on 2 Sept, 2018)
- 2 Indian Institute of Population Sciences (2001), Mumbai
- 3 Kumar, Bhavya (2015), Migrant Workers: An In-visible Community of 80 Million; <https://www.innovairre.com/migrant-workers-invisible-community-80-million/> (accessed on 2 Sept, 2018)
- 4 Ibid
- 5 Indian Institute of Population Sciences (2001), Mumbai
- 6 Ibid
- 7 National Sample Survey Organization, (2012), 68th Round, Govt. of India
- 8 Mahagun Moderne society in Noida attacked: Keep Bangladeshis out chorus emerges; <https://www.financialexpress.com/india-news/mahagun-moderne-society-in-noida-attacked-keep-bangladeshis-out-chorus-emerges/761331/> (ac-cessed on 12 August, 2018)
- 9 www.icsw.org/images/docs/Regions/sasia/pub/Migrant-workers-B-K-Sahu.doc (accessed on 12 Au-gust, 2018)